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RECALIBRATING AMERICAN ENGAGEMENT IN GLOBAL GOVERNANCE: THE RATIONALE BEHIND TRUMP'S INTERNATIONAL WITHDRAWALS

ABSTRACT

This article analyzes President Donald Trump's withdrawal policies within both historical and theoretical frameworks, arguing that they exemplify a form of hegemonic revisionism shaped by the interplay of shifting global dynamics and domestic political pressures. Departing from traditional Hegemonic Stability Theory, the article contends that the United States has behaved as a revisionist power under Trump, selectively undermining or exiting international institutions to recalibrate its commitments in line with perceived national interests. These actions were facilitated by rising protectionist sentiment among key domestic constituencies, which disrupted traditional pro-engagement coalitions and lent credibility to threats of unilateral disengagement. Furthermore, drawing on liberal International Relations theories focused on domestic politics, the article highlights how internal political configurations — especially the influence of social groups and institutional dynamics — have shaped US foreign policy choices during this period. A conceptual distinction is drawn between instrumental disengagement, which involves strategic recalibration within a multilateral framework, and ideological withdrawal, aimed at delegitimizing multilateralism itself. Trump's first term predominantly reflected the former, using exit threats as bargaining tools, while his second term indicated a shift toward the latter, characterized by more explicit repudiation of international institutions. The article concludes by evaluating the implications of this evolving strategy for US credibility, global governance, and the future of multilateral cooperation.

Hegemonic Stability and Hegemonic Revisionism: Theoretical Insights and Empirical Developments

Hegemonic Stability Theory (HST) posits that the presence of a dominant state is essential for sustaining order in the international system¹. According to classical and neorealist scholars, such as Charles Kindleberger and Robert Gilpin, the hegemon underwrites systemic stability by organizing economic and security relations in accordance with its national interests and by providing key public goods, including security and a stable international economy, in exchange for compliance and legitimacy². In this view, the hegemon exercises power not solely through coercion but also through the construction of institutions and norms that embed its leadership in a broader multilateral framework³. Liberal institutionalist interpretations, such as those of G. John Ikenberry, emphasize the self-imposed constraints that hegemonic powers accept in order to reinforce the legitimacy of the liberal international order and deter balancing

¹ WEBB M.C. – KRASNER S.D., *Hegemonic Stability Theory: An Empirical Assessment*, in «Review of International Studies», 15, 2 (1989), pp. 183-198. <http://www.jstor.org/stable/20097178>. Accessed July 5, 2025.

² KINDLEBERGER C.P., *Dominance and Leadership in the International Economy: Exploitation, Public Goods, and Free Rides*, in «International Studies Quarterly», 25, 2 (June 1981), pp. 242-254.

³ GILPIN R., *War and Change in World Politics*, Cambridge, Cambridge University Press, 1981; KINDLEBERGER C.P., *The World in Depression 1929-1939*, Berkeley, University of California Press, 1973.

behavior by allies and rivals⁴. By institutionalizing its dominance, the hegemon gains long-term stability, even at the cost of partially limiting its own autonomy⁵.

However, the empirical trajectory of US foreign policy under the Trump administration challenges this account. Instead of acting as a custodial power preserving the liberal order, the United States increasingly adopted a selective and transactional approach, calling into question the liberal foundations of the postwar order and its commitment to multilateralism. This shift aligns with a different theoretical development, known as Hegemonic Revisionism, which focuses on the transformation, rather than the preservation or decline, of hegemonic powers. In this framework, the hegemon is not primarily committed to preserving the order per se, which may have been initially created to accommodate a different historical context or alliance structure, but rather actively seeks to alter it when its institutional or normative structure no longer aligns with its evolving strategic or domestic interests⁶. Revisionism thus complicates both the realist expectation of stability through dominance and the liberal view of rule-based leadership.

Poletti and Zambenardi offer a critical perspective on the explanatory limitations of traditional hegemonic stability models in understanding the Trump administration's disengagement from multilateral trade governance. They argue that while structural theories effectively capture the long-term dynamics of hegemonic decline, they often overlook the role of domestic political factors in shaping concrete policy outcomes. Their analysis reveals how the increasing politicization of trade policy in the United States generated strong political incentives for Trump to adopt a protectionist and unilateralist trade posture⁷. By linking these domestic developments with broader structural transformations in the global economy, US withdrawal from multilateral trade governance is not simply a symptom of hegemonic decline but an outcome of the interplay between institutional constraints, electoral pressures, and leadership preferences.

For analytic clarity, the article follows Poletti and Zambenardi's distinction between instrumental disengagement, a strategic recalibration of commitments within a broadly multilateral framework, and ideological withdrawal, a deliberate effort to delegitimize the multilateral system itself⁸.

In the case of the Trump administration, both logics are present to varying degrees. While certain institutions were bypassed or delegitimized, others were re-engaged on revised terms aimed at enhancing US leverage. The analysis thus highlights the importance of considering the intersection between structural power shifts and fractured domestic constituencies that empower unilateral tactics in evaluating hegemonic behavior.

In particular, polarization of domestic interest groups reshaped the US policy apparatus, enabling a strategy that leveraged international negotiations as instruments of domestic bargaining rather than collective institution-building. From this vantage point, Trump's strategy does not represent a wholesale rejection of multilateralism, but rather a recalibration of US engagement designed to maximize strategic flexibility and domestic political advantage.

Ultimately, the case of US hegemonic revisionism under Trump illustrates that dominant powers may seek to transform, not simply preserve, the international order when internal and external conditions shift. While the findings remain provisional, given the limitations of a single case study and the uncertain trajectory of future US administrations, they suggest that the sustainability of the liberal international order depends not only on material capabilities but also on the domestic political foundations of hegemonic commitment. Evolving geopolitical dynamics and internal political shifts might alter these revisionist tendencies in future policymaking.

⁴ IKENBERRY G.J., *After Victory: Institutions, Strategic Restraint, and the Rebuilding of Order after Major Wars*, Princeton, Princeton University Press, 2001.

⁵ IKENBERRY G.J., *Liberal Leviathan: The Origins, Crisis, and Transformation of the American World Order*, Princeton, Princeton University Press, 2011.

⁶ POLETTI A. - ZAMBERNARDI L., *Declining hegemony and the sources of Trump's disengagement from multilateral trade governance: the interaction between domestic politics and the international political economy*, in «International Politics» (July 17, 2021). <https://doi.org/10.1057/s41311-021-00346-9>.

⁷ Ibid.

⁸ Ibid.

State of the art

During Donald Trump's first presidential term (2017–2021), the United States, guided by the "America First" foreign policy, withdrew from various international agreements, organizations, and multilateral mechanisms. These included the Trans-Pacific Partnership Agreement (TPP), the Paris Agreement, the Global Compact on Migration, the United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization (UNESCO), the Iran Nuclear Agreement, the United Nations Human Rights Council (UNHRC), the Intermediate-Range Nuclear Forces Treaty, the Open Skies Treaty, and the World Health Organization (WHO), among others. These withdrawals provoked significant controversy within the international community, as they were perceived as a retreat from multilateralism and a challenge to the stability of global governance. The moves coincided with rising domestic protectionism and political realignment, making unilateral exit threats politically viable.

Following President Joe Biden's inauguration, efforts were made to re-engage with several of these institutions. However, despite his administration's decision to rejoin certain organizations, the broader consequences of the previous withdrawals and breaches of international commitments were not fully mitigated. Moreover, the Biden administration faced criticism for what some perceived as an arbitrary approach to international engagement, alternating between withdrawal and re-entry into global institutions without demonstrating a consistent commitment to international norms. Critics argued that this flip-flopping eroded US credibility and suggested a lack of respect and responsibility toward the established global governance frameworks⁹.

Despite the partial restoration of US participation in international organizations, the subsequent return of Donald Trump to the presidency in 2025 marked a renewed phase of disengagement. On January 20, 2025, the day of his second inauguration, Trump signed an executive order announcing the United States' withdrawal from the WHO¹⁰ and the Paris Agreement. This was followed by an order on February 4 to exit the UNHRC, terminate financial contributions to the United Nations Relief and Works Agency for Palestine Refugees in the Near East (UNRWA), and initiate a review of UNESCO to assess its alignment with US interests. Additionally, on February 6, another executive order imposed sanctions on the International Criminal Court officials¹¹.

Trump's second-term approach to multilateralism has been revealed as even more assertive than his first term, signaling a deepened shift toward unilateralism or, as some scholars argue, toward isolationism described as "America Alone" rather than "America First"¹². These actions further strain the United States' credibility and global leadership and pose significant challenges to the operational stability of international organizations and the broader multilateral governance system. The implications of this renewed disengagement extend beyond the immediate political domain, straining alliances and reducing international trust in the US, which is seen as increasingly unpredictable on the world stage. They also raise concerns about the long-term sustainability of international cooperation in addressing global challenges.

Historical precedents and the continuity of "Withdrawal Diplomacy"

Trump's withdrawal strategy is not an entirely novel development in US foreign policy. While the US helped create and lead many multilateral organizations after World War II to shape a liberal international order, over time, some American leaders have come to see the

⁹ EICHENSEHR K., *Biden Administration Reengages with International Institutions and Agreements*, in «American Journal of International Law» 115 (2021), n. 2, pp. 323-329. <https://doi.org/10.1017/ajil.2021.12>.

¹⁰ THE WHITE HOUSE, *Withdrawing the United States from the World Health Organization*, in «Presidential Actions» (January 20, 2025). <https://www.whitehouse.gov/presidential-actions/2025/01/withdrawing-the-united-states-from-the-worldhealth-organization/>.

¹¹ THE WHITE HOUSE, *Withdrawing the United States from and Ending Funding to Certain United Nations Organizations and Reviewing United States Support to All International Organizations*, in «Presidential Actions» (February 4, 2025). <https://www.whitehouse.gov/presidential-actions/2025/02/withdrawing-the-united-states-from-and-ending-funding-to-certain-united-nations-organizations-and-reviewing-united-states-support-to-all-international-organizations/>.

¹² YEOLA K., *The U.S. Withdrawal from International Organizations: What It Means for Global Order?*, in «Modern Diplomacy» (February 10, 2025). <https://modern diplomacy.eu/2025/02/10/the-u-s-withdrawal-from-international-organisations-what-it-means-for-global-order/>.

very system they built as a constraint rather than a tool of dominance. This position reflects a tension at the heart of US foreign policy.

Notably, in 1977, President Jimmy Carter announced the US withdrawal from the International Labour Organization (ILO), marking the first instance of an official disengagement from an international organization¹³. This trend continued under subsequent administrations: President Ronald Reagan refused to ratify the United Nations Convention on the Law of the Sea¹⁴, withdrew from UNESCO¹⁵, and disengaged from the International Court of Justice¹⁶. Similarly, President Bill Clinton led the withdrawal from the United Nations Industrial Development Organization in 1996¹⁷. The George W. Bush administration further exemplified this approach by rejecting the Kyoto Protocol, boycotting the World Conference against Racism, and withdrawing from the Anti-Ballistic Missile Treaty¹⁸.

These actions reflect a pattern of US foreign policy characterized by elements of exceptionalism, isolationism, and nationalism. However, such tendencies must be understood within the broader context of post-1945 US international engagement. The liberal international order, largely shaped by the United States, was designed not only to project American influence but also to institutionalize it within a framework of rules and norms¹⁹. While US leaders have often expressed ambivalence toward the constraints such institutions impose on national autonomy, they have also recognized their strategic value, particularly in legitimizing American leadership and reassuring allies. As Robert Zoellick noted, the United States did not forgo its advantages but frequently moderated its behavior to preserve the system it helped establish²⁰.

Although past administrations have selectively disengaged from international commitments, the Trump administration marked a more assertive and ideologically driven departure from multilateralism. As such, the “America First” doctrine should be seen not merely as a continuation of historical patterns but as a more radical and unilateral rejection of institutional constraints. This shift reflects not only broader structural and domestic dynamics but also Trump’s distinctive leadership style, characterized by transactionalism, self-interest, unpredictability, and a deliberate challenge to the norms underpinning US postwar diplomacy. He perceived international organizations, including NATO, as limiting the United States’ sovereign decision-making, economic interests, and competitiveness²¹. For leaders like Trump – and broader currents in US political thought that favor nationalism and sovereignty – such compromises are seen as unacceptable limitations on America’s freedom to act in its interests. Trump’s critique focused on the idea that international organizations unfairly benefited weaker states at the expense of stronger ones, referring to institutions like the World Trade Organization (WTO), which arguably enabled other countries to “cheat” or “gain unfair

¹³ JOYNER C.C., *The United States’ Withdrawal from the ILO: International Politics in the Labor Arena*, in «International Lawyer» 12, 4 (1978), pp. 707-727. <https://scholar.smu.edu/cgi/viewcontent.cgi?article=3357&context=tul>.

¹⁴ CLARK W.P., *Reagan and the Law of the Sea*, in «The Heritage Foundation» (October 2007). <https://www.heritage.org/global-politics/commentary/reagan-and-the-law-the-sea>.

¹⁵ GWERTZMAN B., *U.S. Is Quitting UNESCO, Affirms Backing for U.N.*, in «The New York Times» (December 30, 1983). <https://www.nytimes.com/1983/12/30/world/us-is-quitting-unesco-affirms-backing-for-un.html>.

¹⁶ SIMON P., *Reagan’s World-Court Error*, in «The New York Times» (October 16, 1985). <https://www.nytimes.com/1985/10/16/opinion/reagan-s-world-court-error.html>.

¹⁷ SCHAEFER B., *The U.S. Should Not Rejoin the United Nations Industrial Development Organization*, in «The Heritage Foundation» (October 29, 2014). <https://www.heritage.org/global-politics/report/the-us-should-not-rejoin-the-united-nations-industrial-development>.

¹⁸ VIDAL J., *Bush Kills Global Warming Treaty*, in «The Guardian» (March 29, 2001). <https://www.theguardian.com/environment/2001/mar/29/globalwarming.usnews>.

¹⁹ IKENBERRY G.J., *After Victory: Institutions, Strategic Restraint, and the Rebuilding of Order after Major Wars*, Princeton, Princeton University Press, 2001.

²⁰ ZOELLICK R., quoted in LUCK E. C., *Mixed Messages: American Politics and International Organization, 1919–1999*, Washington, DC, Brookings Institution Press, 1999, p. 61.

²¹ IKENBERRY G.J., *The Plot Against American Foreign Policy: Can the Liberal Order Survive?*, in «Foreign Affairs» 96, 3 (2017), pp. 2-9. <https://www.foreignaffairs.com/articles/united-states/2017-04-17/plot-against-american-foreign-policy>.

advantages”²², or NATO, which imposes disproportionate burdens on American taxpayers while allowing other member states to “free-ride” on American military protection²³.

From this perspective, international law and multilateral treaties are not neutral frameworks but rather tools that constrain US autonomy. They bind the US to standards and obligations that might not always align with immediate national interests. Moreover, the enforcement mechanisms of these organizations, such as WTO dispute panels or UN Resolutions, can restrict US policy choices or require costly political accommodations. In Trump’s view, true sovereignty demanded the rejection of these “entangling” structures whenever they seemed to limit the pursuit of national advantage.

Ikenberry argues that in a unipolar system - marked by the absence of a systemic peer competitor -US foreign policy would increasingly be shaped by domestic political factors such as partisan polarization, electoral incentives, and the preferences of individual leaders²⁴. In such a context, the United States becomes more insulated from external constraints, while other states remain acutely responsive to shifts in American policy. The Trump administration’s foreign policy behavior largely conformed to this logic, often disregarding allies’ concerns and prioritizing unilateral objectives.

However, it remains uncertain whether this relative detachment can be sustained in the current geopolitical climate. The rise of China, renewed great-power competition, and increasing systemic interdependence raise questions about the continued viability of a foreign policy grounded in domestically driven unilateralism. Nevertheless, the historical record suggests that US leadership has long rested on a strategic balance between dominance and institutional self-restraint, a logic that, so far, Trump’s approach has strained but has not entirely dismantled.

Withdrawing as a strategic policy tool

Beyond merely reducing international commitments, the Trump administration actively leveraged the threat of withdrawal as a strategic tool to exert pressure on international organizations. Even before assuming office, Trump and his advisors – echoing conservative initiatives like *Project 2025* – advocated for reassessing US involvement in multilateral institutions through a cost-benefit lens²⁵. Figures such as John Bolton, Trump’s former National Security Advisor, reinforced this position by opposing the United Nations dues-sharing system and proposing that US contributions be restricted to organizations that directly served national interests.

This approach reflected a broader strategy of coercive diplomacy in multilateral settings²⁶, wherein exit threats served to destabilize institutional equilibria and extract concessions without necessarily incurring the full political costs of withdrawal²⁷. For instance, the Trump administration repeatedly threatened to withdraw from the WTO unless reforms addressed what it perceived as systemic biases, particularly concerning dispute settlement mechanisms

²² WAYNE A., *Trump Wants to Strip China of Its ‘Developing Nation’ WTO Status*, in «Al Jazeera» (July 26, 2019). <https://www.aljazeera.com/economy/2019/7/26/trump-wants-to-strip-china-of-its-developing-nation-wto-status>

²³ GRAY M. – SIEBOLD L., *What Did Trump Say About NATO Funding and What Is Article 5?*, in «Reuters» (February 13, 2024). <https://www.reuters.com/world/what-did-trump-say-about-nato-funding-what-is-article-5-2024-02-12/>.

²⁴ IKENBERRY G.J., *Getting Hegemony Right*, in «The National Interest» 63, Spring 2001. https://www.columbia.edu/itc/sipa/U6800/readings-sm/Ikenberry_Hegemony.pdf

²⁵ BARKER D.W.M., *The Global Dimensions of Project 2025: A Foreign Policy for Authoritarianism*, Kettering Foundation (September 2024). <https://kettering.org/the-global-dimensions-of-project-2025-a-foreign-policy-for-authoritarianism/>.

²⁶ KEOHANE R.O., *Multilateral Coercive Diplomacy: Not “Myths of Empire”*, Duke University (November 2002). https://ciaotest.cc.columbia.edu/special_section/iraq/papers/ker02/ker02.html.

²⁷ HEINKELMANN-WILD T., *Europe Must Prepare for US Withdrawal from Multilateralism – Under Trump or Harris*, in «LSE Blog», (October 29, 2024). <https://blogs.lse.ac.uk/europpblog/2024/10/29/europe-must-prepare-for-us-withdrawal-from-multilateralism-under-trump-or-harris/>.

and China's trade practices²⁸. Similarly, threats to exit the Universal Postal Union in 2018 resulted in renegotiated terms favorable to the United States²⁹.

These threats were rendered credible by actual withdrawals from major agreements, and in doing so, Trump effectively weaponized US membership to maximize leverage. However, while tactically successful in some cases, this approach risked undermining the legitimacy of international institutions and weakening long-term US influence within the global order in what has been perceived as a highly irresponsible foreign policy³⁰. This pattern illustrates a broader shift toward transactional multilateralism, wherein the United States increasingly prioritized national advantage over collective global governance³¹, thereby jeopardizing the credibility and efficacy of the very institutions it once helped build³².

Hegemonic Revisionism in withdrawal decisions

President Trump's approach to international institutions can be interpreted through the lens of hegemonic revisionism, which suggests that dominant powers may seek to reshape international systems to better align with their evolving strategic interests. Rather than maintaining the status quo, they may challenge or withdraw from existing institutions to secure more advantageous terms³³. As mentioned in the previous paragraph, withdrawal, or its threat, in this context, serves as a mechanism for compelling institutional change or circumventing multilateral constraints to renegotiate the terms of US engagement in global governance.

This approach underscores a significant shift from previous administrations and a consequent recalibration of America's role in the international order, prioritizing unilateral and direct influence over traditional multilateral collaborative engagement³⁴; however, it may also be understood in more nuanced terms.

On the one hand, traditionally, hegemonic powers like the US *are* the “status quo”, meaning they want to preserve and defend the international order they helped create³⁵. Meanwhile, revisionism is usually associated with rising powers that seek to change the system. Nevertheless, such dichotomies would oversimplify complex realities, and traditional theories of hegemonic decline might be insufficient to explain this behavior, which is driven by a combination of different factors, including domestic political pressures and international economic competition³⁶. Trump's foreign policy exemplifies a form of “partial” rather than “total” revisionism. His approach is selective, targeting specific institutions or agreements he viewed as disadvantageous to US interests, rather than seeking to dismantle the entire liberal international order (as a revolutionary state might attempt). Importantly, Trump did not propose a coherent alternative system; instead, he aimed to renegotiate or withdraw from what he considered “bad deals.” In this light, his strategy can be seen as an attempt to adjust the existing order to serve American power better; hence, this type of revisionism may serve to

²⁸ SAIFEDDINE M., *One by One...Trump Leads Wholesale Withdrawals from International Organisations*, in «Euronews» (February 7, 2025). <https://www.euronews.com/2025/02/07/one-by-one-trump-leads-wholesale-withdrawals-from-international-organisations>.

²⁹ THE GUARDIAN, *Global Postal Union Reaches Deal to Prevent 'Nightmare' of US Exit*, in «The Guardian» (September 25, 2019). <https://www.theguardian.com/world/2019/sep/25/un-universal-postal-union-mail-deal-trump>.

³⁰ PATRICK S., *The Death of the World America Made*, in «Carnegie Endowment for International Peace» (February 19, 2025). <https://carnegieendowment.org/emissary/2025/02/trump-executive-order-treaties-organizations?lang=en>.

³¹ VAN DAMME S. – MENDES P., *The Future of Multilateralism: A New Era Under Trump's America?*, in «ITSS Verona» (March 2025). <https://www.itssverona.it/the-future-of-multilateralism-a-new-era-under-trumps-america>.

³² BOLTON J., *A U.N. Reform Plan for Trump and Stefanik*, in «Wall Street Journal» (December 2024). <https://www.wsj.com/opinion/a-u-n-reform-plan-for-trump-and-stefanik-united-nations-foreign-policy-funding-71817f3c>.

³³ POLETTI A. – ZAMBERNARDI L., *Declining Hegemony and the Sources of Trump's Disengagement from Multilateral Trade Governance: The Interaction Between Domestic Politics and the International Political Economy*, in «International Politics» 59 (2022), pp. 1101–1118. <https://doi.org/10.1057/s41311-021-00346-9>.

³⁴ MENDES P.E., *The Dynamics of Change in United States Foreign Policy: Contexts, Leadership, and Hegemonic Legitimacy*, in «Social Sciences» 12, 10 (2023), p. 560. <https://doi.org/10.3390/socsci12100560>.

³⁵ GILPIN R., *War and Change in World Politics*, Cambridge University Press, Cambridge 1981.

³⁶ POLETTI A. – ZAMBERNARDI L., *Declining Hegemony and the Sources of Trump's Disengagement from Multilateral Trade Governance: The Interaction Between Domestic Politics and the International Political Economy*, in «International Politics» 59 (2022), pp. 1101–1118. <https://doi.org/10.1057/s41311-021-00346-9>.

preserve and even strengthen US dominance by allowing it to act as both defender and reformer, depending on changing circumstances³⁷. Domestically, Trump's withdrawal strategy resonated with key constituencies within the Republican Party³⁸. Traditional conservatives have long championed national sovereignty and resisted international constraints, and, at the same time, populist factions within the party have opposed globalization and favored economic nationalism. Trump's disengagement from international organizations aligned with these ideological tendencies, bolstering his political support among right-wing and anti-establishment voters and resonating with a segment of the American electorate skeptical of globalization and multilateral commitments³⁹. His rhetoric, often targeting the United Nations for "wasting American taxpayers' money," reinforced his appeal to blue-collar workers and nationalist constituents⁴⁰.

Furthermore, Trump's strategic timing of withdrawals exemplifies how he employed this approach to differentiate himself from his political opponents and predecessors. Notably, Trump's decision to announce or initiate withdrawals on his inauguration day was emblematic of his broader effort to redefine US foreign policy through the lens of domestic political contestation⁴¹. By linking international disengagement to his inaugural messaging, Trump effectively framed multilateralism and global cooperation as the failed policies associated with past administrations.

Moreover, in the last days of his previous presidency, Trump took action to make specific foreign policy decisions more difficult to reverse, limiting the options available to the next administration⁴². This tactic highlighted how withdrawal from international organizations was weaponized as a partisan tool, not merely a matter of strategic recalibration but a means of institutional sabotage. By exiting major international agreements shortly before the end of his term, e.g., beginning formal withdrawal processes from the WHO in 2020, Trump sought to complicate the diplomatic landscape for his successors and to lock in a narrative of American sovereignty being "restored" after decades of perceived capitulation⁴³.

The partisan instrumentalization of international engagement under the Trump administration reflects a broader transformation in US foreign policy, whereby alignment with or rejection of multilateral commitments increasingly serves as a marker of domestic political identity. As Andrew Moravcsik's liberal theory of international politics argues, foreign policy preferences are not shaped solely by external imperatives but are rooted in domestic societal interests and mediated through political institutions⁴⁴. Similarly, Helen Milner emphasizes the importance of domestic structures, such as electoral incentives, interbranch competition, and institutional arrangements, in shaping a state's propensity to cooperate internationally⁴⁵.

Therefore, while systemic pressures linked to hegemonic decline may set the stage for disengagement, the specific trajectories of US withdrawal from multilateral trade governance might be heavily shaped by internal political dynamics. Under Trump, trade policy became a highly politicized issue, no longer dominated by technocratic consensus or interest-group

³⁷ CHAN S., *Challenging the Liberal Order: The US Hegemon as a Revisionist Power*, in «International Affairs» 97 (2021), n. 5, pp. 1335-1352. <https://doi.org/10.1093/ia/iiab074>.

³⁸ VON BORZYSKOWSKI I. – VABULAS F., *Public Support for Withdrawal from International Organizations: Experimental Evidence from the US*, in «The Review of International Organizations» 19 (2024), pp. 809–845. <https://link.springer.com/article/10.1007/s11558-024-09539-2>.

³⁹ KING R., *Elon Musk Appears to Back US Withdrawing from NATO and the UN*, in «New York Post», (March 2, 2025). <https://nypost.com/2025/03/02/us-news/elon-musk-appears-to-back-us-withdrawing-from-nato-the-un/>.

⁴⁰ SCHAEFER B., *What Does Trump 2.0 Mean for the United Nations?*, in «GIS Politics» (January 21, 2025). <https://www.gisreportsonline.com/r/trump-un/>.

⁴¹ THE GUARDIAN, *What Executive Orders Did Trump Sign on Day One?*, in «The Guardian» (January 21, 2025). <https://www.theguardian.com/us-news/2025/jan/20/tump-executive-orders-list>.

⁴² ATWAN I.K., *Trump Administration Sprints to Make Foreign Policy Irreversible Before Elections*, in «Arab Center Washington DC» (October 2020). <https://arabcenterdc.org/resource/trump-administration-sprints-to-make-foreign-policy-irreversible-before-elections/>.

⁴³ MAIZLAND L., *Biden's First Foreign Policy Move: Reentering International Agreements*, in «Council on Foreign Relations» (January 2021). <https://www.cfr.org/in-brief/bidens-first-foreign-policy-move-reentering-international-agreements>.

⁴⁴ MORAVCSIK A., *Taking Preferences Seriously: A Liberal Theory of International Politics*, in «International Organization», 51, 4 (1997), pp. 513-553. <https://doi.org/10.1162/002081897550447>.

⁴⁵ MILNER H., *International Theories of Cooperation Among Nations: Strengths and Weaknesses*, in «World Politics», 44, 3 (1992), pp. 466-496. <https://doi.org/10.2307/2010546>.

bargaining but driven by electoral salience and ideological polarization. As discontent with globalization mobilized key segments of the electorate, the administration's protectionist agenda found both political resonance and strategic utility. In this context, the shift toward unilateralism and the rejection of multilateral trade agreements were not only structurally plausible but also domestically expedient.

Thus, the case illustrates how the recalibration of US global leadership cannot be fully understood without integrating the domestic sources of foreign policy revisionism into the analysis of hegemonic change. In this view, a democratically elected leader representing a nationalist and anti-globalist constituency can pursue revisionist policies even in the absence of relative material and structural hegemonic decline.

Evolution of Trump's withdrawal policies across his two terms

Trump's withdrawal policies evolved significantly between his two terms. While his first administration maintained some level of engagement with international organizations, providing financial support to the UN and cooperating selectively, he is adopting a more aggressive and sweeping approach in his second term. As mentioned in the previous paragraph, this can be understood through an interplay of domestic political developments, international structural changes, and leadership dynamics.

During his first term, President Trump's strategy towards multilateral institutions was essentially a mix of withdrawal threats and selective cooperation. Although he withdrew from agreements like the TPP and the Paris Agreement, the administration still maintained some level of engagement with other institutions, including most of the United Nations' agencies and NATO, albeit while pressing for reforms. So, it is arguable that his first term was characterized by an attempt to renegotiate the terms of US participation rather than a wholesale rejection of multilateralism.

However, by his second term, Trump's approach evolved into a more comprehensive disengagement strategy with an expanded scope, marked by a sharp increase in the number of international organizations targeted for withdrawal, including the WHO, UNRWA, UNHRC, UNESCO, and the Paris Agreement, among others that are still in the process. Considering that immediate disengagement with little room for negotiation was prioritized, these actions reflected not merely dissatisfaction with specific institutions but a broader skepticism towards the very premise of multilateral governance in general.

Several factors may have contributed to this strategic shift. Domestically, unencumbered by the need for re-election, Trump could push policies that were previously too politically risky and enjoy greater political freedom. This also aligns with his current electoral base, which had hardened around an even stronger nationalist, anti-globalist sentiment than in 2016⁴⁶. Furthermore, there have been significant bureaucratic changes within the administration, and many institutionalist voices, such as former Secretary of Defense James Mattis and National Security Advisor H.R. McMaster, have departed, replaced by loyalists who share Trump's skepticism of international institutions⁴⁷. Thus, the latter term's withdrawal policies might also be seen as more explicitly tied to domestic political calculations, reinforcing divisions between the Republican and Democratic parties and contributing to increased partisanship.

Another factor is likely to be the failure of reform efforts during the first term, as the threats of withdrawal, particularly within the WTO⁴⁸. Aiming to force structural reforms to dispute settlement mechanisms showed limited success and fostered a growing disillusionment with the ability of existing institutions to accommodate American interests. Hence, unlike his first term, where disengagement had a symbolic dimension, the second term's actions were part of a systematic strategy to redefine American leadership in global governance and its consequential reassessment.

⁴⁶ DOLAN E., *Why Do Republicans Stick with Trump? New Study Explores the Role of White Nationalism*, in «PsyPost», (June 2024). <https://www.psypost.org/why-do-republicans-stick-with-trump-new-study-explores-the-role-of-white-nationalism/>.

⁴⁷ YERUSHALMY J., *Trump 2.0: Are His Cabinet Picks More Extreme Than in 2016?*, in «The Guardian», (November 15, 2024). <https://www.theguardian.com/us-news/2024/nov/15/donald-trump-cabinet-picks-reaction-gaetz-gabbard-kennedy-hesgeth-rubio-waltz-noem>.

⁴⁸ SCHOTT J., *First Steps Toward WTO Reform*, in «ISPI» (December 2023). <https://www.ispionline.it/en/publication/first-steps-toward-wto-reform-155627>.

Impacts on international organizations and global governance

Trump's withdrawal policies have had profound consequences for international organizations⁴⁹. For instance, the US departure from the WHO created a significant financial shortfall, jeopardizing global health initiatives⁵⁰, including tuberculosis prevention programs⁵¹. Similarly, disengagement from the UN Population Fund threatened reproductive health programs in over 150 countries.

The US withdrawal from the Paris Agreement also disrupted global climate governance⁵². Unlike the previous withdrawal, which required a four-year process, the second withdrawal was executed more rapidly, undermining international climate commitments.⁵³ The potential spillover effects include reduced participation from other states and a weakening of global trust in climate agreements⁵⁴.

The UNHRC, UNRWA, and UNESCO also suffered operational disruptions due to US funding cuts. Trump's withdrawal rhetoric, particularly in the context of US-Israel relations, further strained multilateral human rights efforts and weakened international legal accountability mechanisms⁵⁵.

While Trump's withdrawal policies have been framed as a reinforcement of US sovereignty, they have also led to significant diplomatic and geopolitical consequences. In the short term, these actions align with his political agenda and reduce fiscal expenditures. However, in the longer term, continued disengagement from multilateral institutions risks undermining the foundations of US global leadership. It weakens the country's ability to shape international norms and rules, marginalizes it within key decision-making forums, and may erode the credibility of the liberal order itself.

Moreover, this retreat creates strategic openings for rival powers, particularly China, to expand their influence within existing multilateral frameworks. Unlike the Trump administration's skepticism toward international institutions, China has demonstrated a dual strategy: it seeks to work within established global structures while simultaneously building alternative mechanisms that reflect its own priorities and vision of global governance⁵⁶. Notable examples include the Shanghai Cooperation Organization (SCO), the Belt and Road Initiative (BRI), the Asian Infrastructure Investment Bank (AIIB), and the Regional Comprehensive Economic Partnership (RCEP). Such initiatives contribute to the emergence of a parallel, non-Western-centric order that challenges US dominance not through outright confrontation but through the gradual reconfiguration of institutional influence.

Ultimately, the Trump administration's withdrawal doctrine reflects a broader reorientation of US foreign policy and a strategic recalibration of its role within the global governance architecture. While proponents argue that such disengagement restores national sovereignty and recalibrates burdens within international frameworks, critics warn that it risks eroding US influence and undermining the very institutions that have historically sustained a liberal international order. Whether this trajectory will yield durable strategic advantages or result in

⁴⁹ GOSTIN L. O. et al., *US Withdrawal from WHO Is Unlawful and Threatens Global and US Health and Security*, in «The Lancet» 396, no. 10247 (2020), pp. 293–295. [https://www.thelancet.com/journals/lancet/article/PIIS0140-6736\(20\)31527-0/fulltext](https://www.thelancet.com/journals/lancet/article/PIIS0140-6736(20)31527-0/fulltext).

⁵⁰ JOHNS HOPKINS BLOOMBERG SCHOOL OF PUBLIC HEALTH, *The U.S. and the WHO: An Imperfect but Essential Relationship* (January 30, 2025). <https://publichealth.jhu.edu/2025/the-consequences-of-the-us-withdrawal-from-the-who>.

⁵¹ RICHTER F., *The U.S. Is the Largest Contributor to the WHO*, in «Statista» (January 21, 2025). <https://www.statista.com/chart/33800/top-contributors-to-the-world-health-organization/>.

⁵² PULLINS T. – KNIJENBURG S., *US Withdrawal from the Paris Agreement: Impact and Next Steps*, in «White & Case» (January 21, 2025). <https://www.whitecase.com/insight-alert/us-withdrawal-paris-agreement-impact-and-next-steps>.

⁵³ THE CIRCLE, *The Climate Crisis: There's No Going Back*, in «WWF Magazine», 3 (2021). <https://indd.adobe.com/view/a0888d3f-b4e0-4ff8-a418-d4768ae09813>.

⁵⁴ GOLDBERG M. – McGLINCHEY D., *Five Things to Know About the U.S. Withdrawal from the Paris Agreement*, in «Woodwell Climate Research Center» (January 2025). <https://www.woodwellclimate.org/us-withdrawal-paris-agreement/>.

⁵⁵ AMNESTY INTERNATIONAL AUSTRALIA, *U.S. Withdrawal from UN Human Rights Council Is Performative Disregard for Human Rights* (February 2025). <https://www.amnesty.org.au/u-s-withdrawal-from-un-human-rights-council-is-performative-disregard-for-human-rights/>.

⁵⁶ POLETTI A., ZAMBENARDI L., *Explaining U.S. Disengagement from Multilateral Trade Governance: A Framework for Analysis*, in «International Politics», 59, 6 (2022), pp. 1102–1122.

long-term marginalization within an increasingly multipolar world remains, at the time of writing, an open and pressing question.

Summary and Outlook

Before concluding, it is worth emphasizing that this study is based on a single-case analysis of one presidency over a limited period; thus, its empirical claims are suggestive rather than conclusive. Generalizing from Trump's unprecedented style to all US presidents would be unwarranted. Additionally, the analysis is constrained by the ongoing nature of Trump's second term - events and policies, as well as their effects, are still unfolding; hence, the findings should be interpreted as provisional, reinforcing the statement that attributing systemic change to a single administration must be done cautiously.

Donald Trump's withdrawal from international organizations represents a profound recalibration of American foreign policy, one that both draws from historical patterns of US exceptionalism and departs from them through its scope and ideological fervor. Initially framed as a strategy to renegotiate US participation in multilateral frameworks, Trump's policy evolved over time into a more systematic disengagement, particularly during his second term, culminating in the formal shuttering of the US Agency for International Development. In a symbolic gesture coinciding with the 80th anniversary of the UN, Washington withheld funding for core UN operations, representing one of the most dramatic funding cuts in decades. This transformation was driven by a combination of domestic political pressures, leadership changes, and a growing disillusionment with the effectiveness of multilateral institutions in safeguarding, or prioritizing, American interests.

From the perspective of hegemonic revisionism, Trump's policies can be interpreted as an attempt not to dismantle the international system but to reshape it in ways that reinforce US dominance under conditions perceived as more favorable, simultaneously acting as both the architect and the challenger of the global order. The consequences of these withdrawal strategies have been significant: weakened international institutions, strained alliances, and a perceptible erosion of US influence in global governance. While they satisfied domestic nationalist constituencies, they also undermined the credibility and reliability of the United States as a global partner.

The most recent phase of US "withdrawal diplomacy" may represent not a permanent rupture but a critical inflection point in the evolution of American multilateral engagement. While the Trump administration's retreat from international institutions signaled a sharp turn in US foreign policy, it also exposed the structural vulnerabilities of a liberal international order that is heavily reliant on American stewardship. Whether this trend continues or is reversed remains contingent upon evolving domestic and international conditions.

What is already observable is that one of the most significant developments during this period has been the opening of multilateral space to alternative actors, particularly China. As the United States retrenched, Beijing expanded its footprint within key institutions. In May 2025, China pledged \$500 million over five years to the WHO, becoming the largest state donor following the US withdrawal - an emblematic move that highlights its strategy to strengthen normative influence through institutional engagement⁵⁷. China, in an attempt to promote Beijing's interests, has shown an increasing interest in expanding its presence and shaping international norms, rather than simply rejecting or challenging the existing system. Although whether future US administrations will restore such contributions remains uncertain, by reasserting its influence, the US would curtail Beijing's normative gains and take back the reins of collective security and global development. Moreover, in such a context of a shifting international order, where rising powers increasingly exert normative influence and promote alternative values and principles that diverge from liberal-democratic traditions, renewed US engagement in multilateral arenas - particularly in peacekeeping, global health, climate governance, and human rights - could serve to reassert American moral authority and institutional leadership. Such re-engagement would be especially consequential in domains where soft power and normative appeal remain vital to sustaining global legitimacy and coalition-building.

⁵⁷ YUQI Y. - WEI H., *\$500 Million Pledge Makes China Top WHO Donor After U.S. Withdrawal*, in «Caixin Global» (May 23, 2025). <https://www.caixinglobal.com/2025-05-23/500-million-pledge-makes-china-top-who-donor-after-us-withdrawal-102322304.html>

External factors, such as health-related, environmental, or technological crises, could also drive American engagement. Historically, transnational emergencies have catalyzed bipartisan support for multilateral coordination, such as the COVID-19 pandemic, for example, which revealed the limits of unilateral responses and renewed calls for global cooperation even among domestic skeptics and may compel the US to re-engage multilateral mechanisms, not only out of normative considerations but also out of strategic necessity.

Nonetheless, the future of American multilateralism is far from guaranteed and remains intimately tied to domestic political trends. The politicization of international cooperation in US electoral politics has rendered multilateral commitments a partisan issue, with nationalist rhetoric frequently framing global governance as a threat to national sovereignty. A shift toward reengagement may occur if both elites and voters recognize that global challenges cannot be addressed through unilateralism. Conversely, continued entrenchment may result from persistent nationalist rhetoric, the normalization of China's leadership within the UN system, or the strategic preference for regional and bilateral arrangements over multilateral forums.

Whether the longer-term result will be a temporary anomaly or a sustained transformation of American foreign policy remains to be seen. What is clear, however, is that Trump's withdrawal diplomacy is altering the dynamics of US engagement with the world, raising critical questions about the future of multilateralism in an increasingly fragmented international system. If the United States chooses neither to lead nor to follow, the global system may slide into fragmentation. Scholars warn of a looming "multipolar disorder," in which no single set of rules governs international behavior and competing blocs pursue diverging agendas. In such a scenario, global public goods, from climate stability to pandemic preparedness, would depend on ad hoc coalitions rather than inclusive, rule-based institutions⁵⁸. Middle powers and smaller states could find themselves caught between rival spheres of influence, diminishing their agency in global decision-making processes.

This marks a decisive departure from the postwar vision of a cooperative, liberal order grounded in reciprocity, institutionalization, and shared norms. The normative implications of American hegemonic revisionism are, therefore, troubling. By refusing to uphold or even selectively revising the institutions it once championed, the US has ceded both strategic initiative and moral high ground, as well as normative legitimacy. Unless allies and like-minded states can collectively sustain the multilateral order - or a future American administration reverses course - the global system risks entering a period of heightened multipolar uncertainty, diminished cooperation, and strategic instability⁵⁹. This deep uncertainty underscores the stakes of America's current trajectory.

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⁵⁸ KUPCHAN C., BREMMER I., *The Coming Multipolar Disorder*, in «Foreign Affairs» (February 2021). <https://www.foreignaffairs.com/articles/world/2021-02-16/coming-multipolar-disorder>

⁵⁹ IKENBERRY G. J., *The Plot Against American Foreign Policy: Can the Liberal Order Survive?*, in «Foreign Affairs» 96, 3 (2017), pp. 2–9.

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